

IN SURVEYS ON THE USE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN MANAGEMENT AND HOUSING STOCK

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Abstract. *This study investigates the utilization of innovative methods in both management practices and housing stock within contemporary contexts. With rapid advancements in technology and evolving societal needs, the housing sector faces increasing pressure to embrace innovative solutions. Through comprehensive surveys conducted across diverse demographics, this research explores the extent to which innovative methods are integrated into management strategies and the maintenance of housing stock. Key areas of focus include the implementation of technology-driven solutions, sustainability initiatives, and adaptive management approaches. By analyzing survey data, this study aims to provide insights into current trends, challenges, and opportunities associated with the adoption of innovation in housing management. Findings from this research offer valuable implications for policymakers, industry professionals, and stakeholders seeking to enhance efficiency, sustainability, and quality of housing management practices in the modern era.*

Key words: *lean production, management efficiency, innovative approaches, housing and communal services, quality management, public-private partnership, market relations.*

The resumption and development of any type of activity occurs primarily through improving the methods of its implementation. Consequently, there is a need to introduce innovative conceptual approaches to improving management, which determine the innovative strategy of any activity. One of the modern ways to improve management efficiency and improve its efficiency is the implementation of the Lean Production concept. Many successful companies in the global market demonstrate their achievements and positions by the effectiveness of this approach.

Despite the fact that many leading In foreign countries, the economical production method has been widely used in recent years and has become very popular ; in our country, the use of this management method is not at the required level, or most enterprises and organizations do not even have an idea about it.

The concept of Lean Production (economical production) is based on the management principles of the Japanese company Toyota (Toyota) and its essence is to eliminate all types of losses, that is, the main idea in it is to simplify production as much as possible and eliminate losses.

The term Lean Production first appeared in March 1988, according to John Kraftsik's article on the Lean Manufacturing Triumph, based on research from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. In this case, he relied on his experience as a quality engineer at Toyota 's California division.

Lean manufacturing is an innovative approach to quality management that aims to optimize production processes, reduce costs, improve product quality and meet customer expectations.

In general, "Lean Manufacturing" represents the involvement of all employees in optimizing business processes and being as market-oriented as possible.

The most popular and widely used tools of modern lean manufacturing are 5S, Andon , Kaizen , Muda , PDCA and many others.

Sometimes they use the name of one of the elements of this system " *JIT* " (Just-in-time, "just-in-time-production") to fully understand the concept.

The use of innovative methods and approaches to improve the level of scientific resource management is becoming increasingly relevant today. It is no coincidence that this is one of the most important reserves for increasing labor productivity in the housing and communal services sector. Management of resources and reserves means the efficient use of electricity, heat, gas, labor and much more in the housing and communal services sector on an innovative basis (from the point of view of innovation), taking into account social needs.

In order to improve the housing and communal services market today, the main attention should be paid to innovative development. It is the current state of innovative management and its tasks that allow us to think about the emerging realities in the field of reforming the housing and communal services.

In this context, we believe that taking into account that the concept of lean production, which is currently widely used in international best practices, represents an innovative approach to modern quality management aimed at optimizing production processes, reducing costs, improving product quality and meeting consumer expectations, it is advisable to apply this management method in the field of public services, in particular, in the field of management and regulation of housing construction in our country.

For example, the introduction of a lean production approach in the municipal sector, especially in housing and communal services, is relevant and has been confirmed both in foreign and Russian practice.

It is estimated that 30 to 50 percent of costs in service organizations are costs caused by customer satisfaction or slow processing speeds.

In general, eliminating problems in the industry, in turn, requires an integrated approach. To do this, it is necessary to improve the system of management and regulation of housing construction on the basis of public-private partnership in this area as a result of the transition of housing and communal services to market relations, the implementation of the general direction of reforming the industry and the phased out of budget financing.

In our opinion, as a result of introducing the concept of lean production to improve the management of the housing stock in the republic, we can achieve the following results:

- formation of a culture and skills for the effective and rational use of resources (human, material, financial and temporary) in the minds of all employees working in the industry;
- improving the institutionally perfect organizational and legal framework for the activities of private homeowners' partnerships and the use of housing stock in accordance with market requirements;
- maximum simplification of the organization of the housing and communal services system and the elimination of unnecessary costs, as well as providing more services with a shorter time interval ;
- the formation of a systematic approach to organizing the provision of services to the population in the field of housing and communal services, including control of its quality;
- ensuring the development of innovative methods in the industry by introducing modern innovative and information technologies in the service sector and creating the highest possible

consumer value for investors;

- increasing the efficiency of the housing stock system through the formation of a cooperative chain of cooperation between all public utilities;
- with the creation of an economical production (service) system based on the principle of “just in time with minimal costs” for the repair of housing stock.

To summarize, we can say that the successful implementation of the concept of lean production in the sphere of public utilities of the republic, in particular, housing management, effectively used in the practice of areas and industries of advanced foreign countries , can become a significant contribution to increasing the efficiency of reforms carried out in the system.

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